

HEAT PUMP HVAC SYSTEM AS PART OF AN INTEGRATED RES SYSTEM FOR THE INDOOR CLIMATE CONTROL OF A LYING HEN HOUSE

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ABSTRACT

Lately, much of the academic community's research efforts have been directed towards the transition from fossil fuel dependence in European husbandry facilities to fostering a sustainable livestock sector. To this end and in the framework of the H2020 RES4LIVE project (GA No. 101000785), a study investigation is conducted in an experimental laying hens facility at the Agricultural University of Athens (AUA), to evaluate the use of an integrated Renewable Energy Source (RES) instead of fossil fuel, while enhancing animal welfare and productivity. The core of the system consists of a heat pump (HP) designed primarily to condition the indoor air by heating, cooling, and dehumidifying it, combined with a solar photovoltaic (PV) system to generate electricity, covering part of the heat pump's consumption.

The present study focuses on the results obtained during the testing and monitoring of the innovative HP using a sensor-based monitoring system that collects data on system performance and indoor conditions. Focusing on two particular periods, summer and winter, the initial findings suggest that the HP technology seems to present the potential to enhance animal welfare by maintaining suitable indoor air temperatures and relative humidity into the desired range, especially during heatwaves where the previous conventional heating and ventilation systems were considerably inadequate. The HP achieves a Coefficient of Performance (COP) in the range of 2.5 to 3.5 during summer (cooling), and 3.0 to 4.7 during winter (heating), respectively. The results contribute to expanding our understanding of incorporating RES into livestock systems.